

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

S1. CONSIDERATION OF SURROGATE ENDPOINTS IN METHODOLOGICAL GUIDELINES

Country Agency (acronym)	Methodological document [name (year), source, link]	Use of surrogates considered?	Surrogate definition provided?	Examples of surrogates listed?	Acceptability criteria provided?	Evidence strength assessment provided?	Validation methods provided?	Validation values provided?
Austria AT GÖG	Methodenhandbuch für Health Technology Assessment (2012) https://jasmin.goeg.at/121/	Yes	Yes					
Austria AT LBI-HTA	Externes Manual. Selbstverständnis und Arbeitsweise. Teil 1. HTA-Projektbericht 03 (2007/2009) http://eprints.hta.lbg.ac.at/714/1/HTA-Projektbericht_003.pdf	Yes						
AT LBI-HTA	Internes Manual. Abläufe und Methoden. Teil 2 (2. Aufl.). HTA-Projektbericht 06 (2011/2017), http://eprints.hta.lbg.ac.at/713/3/HTA-Projektbericht_06_(2.Auflage).pdf	Yes		Yes				
BE KCE	Belgian guidelines for economic evaluations and budget impact analyses: second edition (2012) (https://www.kce.fgov.be/sites/default/files/atoms/files/KCE_183_economic_evaluations_second_edition_Report_update.pdf)	Yes						
BE KCE	KCE Process Book (2012) 9 http://processbook.kce.fgov.be/node/117 http://processbook.kce.fgov.be/node/133	Yes						
BG NCPHA	Ordinance № 9 / 1.12.2015	Yes	Yes	Yes				
CR AAZ	Croatian Ordinance of the Ministry of Health related to pharma and medical devices (2014), HZZO webpage, http://www.hzzo.hr/wp-content/uploads/2014/01/Pravilnik.pdf?b32def							
CR AAZ	The Croatian Guideline for Health Technology Assessment - Process and Reporting (2011), AAZ webpage, http://aaz.hr/sites/default/files/hrvatske_smjernice_za_procjenu_zdravstvenih_tehnologija.pdf	Yes						
DE DIMDI	Methoden zur vergleichenden Bewertung pharmazeutischer Produkte (2005) https://portal.dimdi.de/de/hta/hta_berichte/hta122_bericht_de.pdf							
DE DIMDI	Surrogatenendpunkte als Parameter der Nutzenbewertung (2009), DIMDI https://portal.dimdi.de/de/hta/hta_berichte/hta250_bericht_de.pdf	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes			
DE G-BA	Anlage II.6: Modul 4 - Medizinischer Nutzen und medizinischer Zusatznutzen, Patientengruppen mit therapeutisch bedeutsamem Zusatznutzen	Yes			Yes	Yes		

Country Agency (acronym)	Methodological document [name (year), source, link]	Use of surrogates considered?	Surrogate definition provided?	Examples of surrogates listed?	Acceptability criteria provided?	Evidence strength assessment provided?	Validation methods provided?	Validation values provided?
	https://www.g-ba.de/downloads/17-98-3528/2013-04-18_An12_6_Modul4.pdf							
DE G-BA	Verfahrensordnung des Gemeinsamen Bundesausschusses Stand: 6. Juli 2018 https://www.g-ba.de/downloads/62-492-1614/VerfO_2018-03-16_iK-2018-07-05.pdf							
DE iQWIG	Allgemeine Methoden (2017), iQWIG https://www.iqwig.de/download/Allgemeine-Methoden_Version-5-0.pdf .				Yes	Yes	Yes	
DE iQWIG	Aussagekraft von Surrogatendpunkten in der Onkologie (2011), iQWIG, https://www.iqwig.de/download/A10-05_Rapid_Report_Version_1-1_Surrogatendpunkte_in_der_Onkologie.pdf	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
ES AETS	Guía para la elaboración de informes de evaluación de tecnologías sanitarias (1999), AETS website, http://gesdoc.isciii.es/gesdoccontroller?action=download&id=07/11/2012-8a8470ba07	Yes			Yes			
ES AETSA	Guía para la elaboración de informes de evaluación de medicamentos (2013), AETSA webpage, http://www.aetsa.org/produccion-cientifica/	Yes			Yes			
ES AVALIA-T	Observación de tecnologías sanitarias después de su introducción en la práctica clínica. Priorización y propuesta de protocolo de evaluación. (2009)	Yes						
FR HAS	Choix méthodologiques pour l'évaluation économique à la HAS (2011), https://www.has-sante.fr/portail/jcms/c_1120708/fr/guide-choix-methodologiques-pour-l-evaluation-economique-a-la-has	Yes			Yes			
GR EOPPY	Appendix I: Methodology for health Assessment of medicinal products for human use	Yes			Yes			
HU NIPN	Health economic guideline of the Ministry of Human Resources (Az Emberi Erőforrások Minisztériuma szakmai irányelve az egészség-gazdaságtani elemzések készítéséhez (print: Egészségügyi Közlöny LXIII. évf., 3. szám web: https://www.obdk.hu)) (2017), in Hungarian: http://www.hbcs.hu/uploads/jogszabaly/2481/fajlok/egeszsegugyi_technologia_ertekeles.pdf , in English: https://www.ispor.org/PEguidelines/source/HTA_Guideline_HUN_eng.pdf	Yes			Yes			
IE HIQA	Guidelines for Economic Evaluation of Health Technologies in Ireland (2018) https://www.hiqa.ie/sites/default/files/2018-01/HIQA_Economic_Guidelines_2018.pdf	Yes						
IE HIQA	Guidelines for Evaluating the Clinical Effectiveness of Health Technologies in Ireland (2014) https://www.hiqa.ie/sites/default/files/2017-01/Clinical-Effectiveness-Guidelines.pdf	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes			

Country	Methodological document [name (year), source, link]	Use of surrogates considered?	Surrogate definition provided?	Examples of surrogates listed?	Acceptability criteria provided?	Evidence strength assessment provided?	Validation methods provided?	Validation values provided?
IT AIFA	CRITERI PER LA VALUTAZIONE DELL'INNOVATIVITA' http://www.aifa.gov.it/sites/default/files/Allegato1_criteri_valutazione_innovativita.pdf			Yes	Yes			
NL ZIN	Beoordeling stand van de wetenschap en praktijk, in English: Assessment of 'established medical science and medical practice' (update 2015) https://www.zorginstituutnederland.nl/publicaties/rapport/2015/01/15/beoordeling-stand-van-de-wetenschap-en-praktijk	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes		
NL ZIN	Guideline for economic evaluations in healthcare (2016) https://english.zorginstituutnederland.nl/publications/reports/2016/06/16/guideline-for-economic-evaluations-in-healthcare	Yes			Yes			
NO NIPH	Håndbok for Nasjonalt kunnskapssenter for helsetjenesten (2015)	Yes						
NO NIPH	Template/Guidance for submission of documentation for Single Technology Assessment of medical device, diagnostic methods and procedures	Yes						
PL AOTMiT		Yes						
PT INFARMED	Metodologia para Avaliação Farmacoterapêutica (2016), Webpage Infarmed, http://www.infarmed.pt/documents/15786/1963929/Metodologia+CATS/77f97467-01a9-4a82-8012-d6a608f420e1	Yes			Yes		Yes	
PT INFARMED	Orientações metodológicas para estudos de avaliação económica de medicamentos (1998), Webpage Infarmed, http://www.infarmed.pt/web/infarmed/avaliacao-terapeutica-e-economica	Yes						
SE SBU	Assessment of methods in health care, April 2018 https://www.sbu.se/contentassets/76adf07e270c48efaf67e3b560b7c59c/eng_metodboken.pdf	Yes	Yes	Yes				
SE TLV	General guidelines for economic evaluations from the Pharmaceutical Benefits Board (LFNAR 2003:2) https://www.tlv.se/download/18.2e53241415e842ce95514e9/1510316396792/Guidelines-for-economic-evaluations-LFNAR-2003-2.pdf	Yes						
SK MoH	Pharmaco-economic guideline (Metodická pomôcka k vyhláške Ministerstva zdravotníctva Slovenskej republiky č. 343/2008 Z. z. o podrobnostiach farmako-ekonomického rozboru lieku, k vyhláške Ministerstva zdravotníctva Slovenskej republiky č. 210/2008 Z. z., ktorou sa ustanovujú podrobnosti o medicínsko-ekonomickom rozbore zdravotníckej pomôcky a k vyhláške Ministerstva zdravotníctva Slovenskej republiky č. 149/2009 Z. z. o podrobnostiach medicínsko-ekonomického rozboru dietickej potraviny) (2009), MoH SK, http://www.health.gov.sk/?farmako-ekonomicky-rozbor-lieku , http://www.health.gov.sk/Zdroje?Sources/dokumenty/dieticke_potraviny /Metodicka_pomocka_FE_a_ME_rozbor.rtf	Yes			Yes			

Country Agency (acronym)	Methodological document [name (year), source, link]	Use of surrogates considered?	Surrogate definition provided?	Examples of surrogates listed?	Acceptability criteria provided?	Evidence strength assessment provided?	Validation methods provided?	Validation values provided?
UK AWMMSG	AWMSG POLICY ON APPRAISING LIFE-EXTENDING, END-OF-LIFE MEDICINES (2016) http://www.awmsg.org/docs/awmsg/appraisaldocs/inforandforms/AWMSG%20policy%20on%20appraising%20life%20extending%20end%20of%20life%20medicines.pdf			Yes				
UK AWMMSG	FORM B GUIDANCE NOTES (2018) - This document provides guidance to applicant companies on the completion of Form B. Form B contains the detailed appraisal submission. http://www.awmsg.org/docs/awmsg/appraisaldocs/inforandforms/Form%20B%20guidance%20notes.pdf	Yes		Yes	Yes			
UK NICE	A review of studies examining the relationship between progression-free survival and overall survival in advanced or metastatic cancer http://nicedsu.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/PFSOS-Report.FINAL_06.08.12.pdf	Yes		Yes	Yes			
UK NICE	Guide to the methods of technology appraisal 2013 (2013), https://www.nice.org.uk/process/pmg31/chapter/introduction	Yes	Yes	Yes				
UK NICE	Medical technologies evaluation programme methods guide (2017), https://www.nice.org.uk/process/pmg33/	Yes						
UK NICE	Single technology appraisal: User guide for company evidence submission template (2015), https://www.nice.org.uk/process/pmg24/	Yes						
AU MSAC	Technical Guidelines for preparing assessment reports for the Medical Services Advisory Committee – Medical Service Type: Therapeutic (Version 2.0), March 2016 http://www.msac.gov.au/internet/msac/publishing.nsf/Content/9C7DCF1C2DD56CBECA25801000123C32/\$File/TherapeuticTechnicalGuidelines-Final-March2016-Version2.0-accessible.pdf	Yes			Yes	Yes		
AU PBAC	Guidelines for preparing a submission to the Pharmaceutical Benefits Advisory Committee (2016) https://pbac.pbs.gov.au/content/information/files/pbac-guidelines-version-5.pdf Glossary version 1 http://www.pbs.gov.au/industry/useful-resources/glossary/Glossary-of-Terms_Final-15Apr-13.pdf	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
CA CADTH	Addendum to CADTH's Guidelines for the Economic Evaluation of Health Technologies: Specific Guidance for Oncology Products (2009) https://www.cadth.ca/sites/default/files/pdf/H0405_Guidance_for_Oncology_Products_gr_e.pdf	Yes	Yes		Yes		Yes	
CA CADTH	Guidelines for the Economic Evaluation of Health Technologies: Canada (2006) https://www.cadth.ca/sites/default/files/pdf/186_EconomicGuidelines_e.pdf	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes			

Country Agency (acronym)	Methodological document [name (year), source, link]	Use of surrogates considered?	Surrogate definition provided?	Examples of surrogates listed?	Acceptability criteria provided?	Evidence strength assessment provided?	Validation methods provided?	Validation values provided?
CA CADTH	Procedure and Submission Guidelines for the CADTH Common Drug Review, August 2018 https://cadth.ca/sites/default/files/cdr/process/Procedure_and_Guidelines_for_CADTH_CDR.pdf	Yes						
EU EUNETHTA	Endpoints used in Relative Effectiveness Assessment: Surrogate Endpoints [(2015), https://www.eunetha.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/surrogate_endpoints.pdf]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
AU MSAC	Technical Guidelines for preparing assessment reports for the Medical Services Advisory Committee – Medical Service Type: Therapeutic (Version 2.0), March 2016 http://www.msac.gov.au/internet/msac/publishing.nsf/Content/9C7DCF1C2DD56CBECA25801000123C32/\$File/TherapeuticTechnicalGuidelines-Final-March2016-Version2.0-accessible.pdf	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		
AU PBAC	Guidelines for preparing a submission to the Pharmaceutical Benefits Advisory Committee (2016) https://pbac.pbs.gov.au/content/information/files/pbac-guidelines-version-5.pdf Glossary version 1 http://www.pbs.gov.au/industry/useful-resources/glossary/Glossary-of-Terms_Final-15Apr-13.pdf	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
CA CADTH	Addendum to CADTH's Guidelines for the Economic Evaluation of Health Technologies: Specific Guidance for Oncology Products (2009) https://www.cadth.ca/sites/default/files/pdf/H0405_Guidance_for_Oncology_Products_gr_e.pdf	Yes	Yes		Yes			
CA CADTH	Guidelines for the Economic Evaluation of Health Technologies: Canada (2006) https://www.cadth.ca/sites/default/files/pdf/186_EconomicGuidelines_e.pdf	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes			
CA CADTH	Procedure and Submission Guidelines for the CADTH Common Drug Review, August 2018 https://cadth.ca/sites/default/files/cdr/process/Procedure_and_Guidelines_for_CADTH_CDR.pdf	Yes						